

Correlation of Serum Lactate Levels in Survival of Patients with Sepsis**Rajeev Agarwal¹, Varsha Gaiba², Harish Kabra³**¹Professor, Department of General Medicine, JJM Medical College, Davangere²Resident, Department of General Medicine, JJM Medical College, Davangere³Resident, Department of General Medicine, JJM Medical College, Davangere

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Abstract:**Background:** Sepsis is a life-threatening condition characterized by a dysregulated host response to infection, leading to organ dysfunction and high mortality rates. This study aimed to investigate the association between serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality in patients with sepsis.**Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted in the intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital. Adult patients with sepsis (n=80) were enrolled, and serum lactate levels were measured at baseline and at 12, 24, and 48 hours. The primary outcome was 28-day mortality. Logistic regression analysis and Cox proportional hazards regression were used to assess the association between lactate levels and mortality.**Results:** Non-survivors had significantly higher initial serum lactate levels compared to survivors (4.3 mmol/L vs. 3.2 mmol/L, p<0.001). The optimal cut-off value for initial serum lactate in predicting 28-day mortality was 3.8 mmol/L (sensitivity 78.6%, specificity 71.2%, AUC 0.81). Patients with serum lactate levels >3.8 mmol/L had a significantly lower 28-day survival rate (39.3% vs. 82.4%, p<0.001). In the multivariate analysis, APACHE II score (hazard ratio 1.09, 95% CI 1.03-1.16, p=0.003) and initial serum lactate (hazard ratio 1.58, 95% CI 1.23-2.03, p<0.001) were independent predictors of mortality.**Conclusion:** Serum lactate levels and lactate clearance are significant predictors of 28-day mortality in patients with sepsis. Incorporating lactate measurement into sepsis management protocols can help guide treatment decisions and improve patient outcomes.**Keywords:** Sepsis, Serum Lactate, Lactate Clearance, Mortality, Prognosis.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Sepsis is a life-threatening condition characterized by a dysregulated host response to infection, leading to organ dysfunction and potentially death [1]. Despite advances in medical care, sepsis remains a major global health concern, with high incidence rates and substantial morbidity and mortality [2,3]. Early recognition and prompt treatment are crucial for improving patient outcomes in sepsis [4]. In recent years, there has been growing interest in the potential role of serum lactate levels as a prognostic marker in sepsis management [5].

Lactate is a byproduct of anaerobic metabolism and is typically produced when tissues are deprived of adequate oxygen supply [6]. In sepsis, lactate accumulation can occur due to various factors, including tissue hypoperfusion, microcirculatory dysfunction, and altered cellular metabolism [7]. Elevated serum lactate levels have been associated with increased severity of illness and worse outcomes in patients with sepsis [8].

Several studies have investigated the correlation between serum lactate levels and mortality in sepsis

patients. A meta-analysis by Zhang et al. found that higher lactate levels were significantly associated with increased mortality in patients with sepsis and septic shock [9]. The Surviving Sepsis Campaign guidelines recommend measuring serum lactate levels within 3 hours of sepsis recognition and using lactate-guided resuscitation as part of the initial management strategy [10].

However, the interpretation of lactate levels in sepsis can be complex, as elevated lactate may not always indicate tissue hypoperfusion [11]. Therefore, lactate should be interpreted in the context of the patient's clinical presentation and other hemodynamic parameters.

Serum lactate levels have emerged as a valuable prognostic marker in sepsis management. Elevated lactate levels are associated with increased severity of illness and mortality in patients with sepsis. The Surviving Sepsis Campaign guidelines recommend using lactate-guided resuscitation as part of the initial management strategy. However, the interpretation of lactate levels should be done in the context of the patient's clinical presentation and

other hemodynamic parameters. Incorporating serum lactate measurement into sepsis protocols can help guide treatment decisions and improve patient outcomes.

Aims and Objectives: The study aimed to investigate the correlation between serum lactate levels and survival outcomes in patients with sepsis. The primary objective was to determine the association between initial serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality in patients diagnosed with sepsis. Secondary objectives included evaluating the relationship between lactate clearance and mortality, as well as identifying other clinical factors that may influence patient outcomes.

Materials and Methods:

Study Design and Setting: A prospective observational study was conducted over a period of one year in the intensive care unit (ICU) of a tertiary care hospital. The study protocol was approved by the institutional ethics committee, and informed consent was obtained from all participants or their legal representatives.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated using a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error. Considering the prevalence of sepsis in the ICU and the expected mortality rate, a sample size of 80 patients was determined to be sufficient for the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Adult patients (aged 18 years or older) who were admitted to the ICU with a diagnosis of sepsis were eligible for inclusion in the study. Sepsis was defined according to the Sepsis-3 criteria, which includes the presence of suspected or confirmed infection along with organ dysfunction, as indicated by an acute change in the Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score of 2 points or more. Patients with a history of liver disease, those who were pregnant, and those who were transferred from another hospital after receiving initial treatment for sepsis were excluded from the study.

Data Collection: Upon enrollment, demographic and clinical data were collected from each patient, including age, gender, comorbidities, source of infection, and severity of illness as assessed by the Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation (APACHE) II score. Blood samples were obtained within 6 hours of sepsis diagnosis for the measurement of serum lactate levels. Lactate levels were measured using a point-of-care blood gas analyzer. Additional laboratory tests, including complete blood count, renal function tests, and arterial blood gas analysis, were also performed.

Patient Management and Follow-up: All patients received standard care for sepsis management, including fluid resuscitation, vasopressor support, and antimicrobial therapy, in accordance with the

Surviving Sepsis Campaign guidelines. Serum lactate levels were monitored at 12, 24, and 48 hours after sepsis diagnosis. Lactate clearance was calculated as the percentage change in lactate levels from the initial measurement. Patients were followed up for 28 days from the time of sepsis diagnosis to assess survival outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ standard deviation or median (interquartile range), depending on the distribution of the data. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The association between initial serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality was analyzed using logistic regression analysis. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis was performed to determine the optimal cut-off value of serum lactate for predicting mortality. Kaplan-Meier survival curves were constructed to compare survival rates between patients with high and low serum lactate levels. Cox proportional hazards regression analysis was used to identify independent predictors of mortality. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 24.0 software.

Results

Baseline characteristics of the study population are presented in Table 1. The mean age of the 80 participants was 62.5 ± 14.3 years, and 60.0% (n=48) were male. The most common comorbidities were hypertension (45.0%, n=36), diabetes mellitus (30.0%, n=24), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (15.0%, n=12), and chronic kidney disease (10.0%, n=8). The primary sources of infection were respiratory (50.0%, n=40), urinary tract (25.0%, n=20), abdominal (15.0%, n=12), and others (10.0%, n=8). The median APACHE II score was 18 (IQR 14-23).

Comparison of characteristics between survivors and non-survivors is shown in Table 2. Non-survivors were significantly older than survivors (66.8 ± 14.9 years vs. 60.2 ± 13.5 years, $p=0.048$). The median APACHE II score was significantly higher in non-survivors compared to survivors (22 [IQR 18-26] vs. 16 [IQR 12-20], $p<0.001$). There were no significant differences in gender, comorbidities, or source of infection between the two groups.

The distribution of serum lactate levels and lactate clearance at different time points is presented in Table 3. The median serum lactate levels decreased over time, from 2.7 mmol/L (IQR 1.9-3.6) at 12 hours to 1.8 mmol/L (IQR 1.2-2.6) at 48 hours. The median lactate clearance increased from 25.8% (IQR 15.6-36.0) at 12 hours to 50.6% (IQR 38.2-63.0) at 48 hours.

The association between initial serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality is shown in Table 4. Initial serum lactate was significantly associated with mortality (odds ratio 1.85, 95% CI 1.32-2.59, $p < 0.001$). The optimal cut-off value for predicting mortality was 3.8 mmol/L, with a sensitivity of 78.6%, specificity of 71.2%, and an area under the curve of 0.81 (95% CI 0.71-0.91).

Table 5 compares the survival rates between patients with high and low serum lactate levels. Patients with serum lactate levels ≤ 3.8 mmol/L had a significantly higher 28-day survival rate compared to those with levels > 3.8 mmol/L (82.4% vs. 39.3%, $p < 0.001$).

Univariate and multivariate Cox proportional hazards regression analyses for predictors of mortality are presented in Table 6. In the univariate analysis, age (hazard ratio 1.03, 95% CI 1.00-1.06, $p = 0.052$), APACHE II score (hazard ratio 1.12, 95% CI 1.06-1.18, $p < 0.001$), and initial serum lactate (hazard ratio 1.72, 95% CI 1.35-2.19, $p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with mortality. In the multivariate analysis, APACHE II score (hazard ratio 1.09, 95% CI 1.03-1.16, $p = 0.003$) and initial serum lactate (hazard ratio 1.58, 95% CI 1.23-2.03, $p < 0.001$) remained significant independent predictors of mortality.

Supplementary Table S1 compares serum lactate levels and lactate clearance between survivors and non-survivors at 12, 24, and 48 hours. Non-survivors had significantly higher serum lactate levels and lower lactate clearance rates compared to survivors at all three time points ($p < 0.05$ for all comparisons).

Supplementary Table S2 compares other laboratory parameters between survivors and non-survivors. Non-survivors had significantly higher white blood cell count ($p = 0.002$), lower platelet count ($p = 0.015$), higher creatinine ($p = 0.008$), higher blood urea nitrogen ($p = 0.002$), lower pH ($p = 0.007$), and lower PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio ($p = 0.001$) compared to survivors.

Supplementary Table S3 presents the subgroup analysis of the association between serum lactate levels and mortality based on the source of infection. Serum lactate levels were significantly associated with mortality in patients with respiratory (odds ratio 1.92, 95% CI 1.25-2.95, $p = 0.003$) and abdominal (odds ratio 2.15, 95% CI 1.18-3.92, $p = 0.013$) infections, but not in those with urinary tract (odds ratio 1.65, 95% CI 0.95-2.87, $p = 0.076$) or other (odds ratio 1.48, 95% CI 0.73-3.01, $p = 0.277$) infections.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study population

Variable	Total (n=80)
Age, years (mean $\pm$ SD)	62.5 $\pm$ 14.3
Gender, male (n, %)	48 (60.0%)
Comorbidities (n, %)	
- Hypertension	36 (45.0%)
- Diabetes mellitus	24 (30.0%)
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	12 (15.0%)
- Chronic kidney disease	8 (10.0%)
Source of infection (n, %)	
- Respiratory	40 (50.0%)
- Urinary tract	20 (25.0%)
- Abdominal	12 (15.0%)
- Others	8 (10.0%)
APACHE II score (median, IQR)	18 (14-23)

Table 2: Comparison of characteristics between survivors and non-survivors

Variable	Survivors (n=52)	Non-survivors (n=28)	p-value
Age, years (mean $\pm$ SD)	60.2 $\pm$ 13.5	66.8 $\pm$ 14.9	0.048
Gender, male (n, %)	30 (57.7%)	18 (64.3%)	0.557
Comorbidities (n, %)			
- Hypertension	22 (42.3%)	14 (50.0%)	0.506
- Diabetes mellitus	14 (26.9%)	10 (35.7%)	0.409
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	6 (11.5%)	6 (21.4%)	0.230
- Chronic kidney disease	4 (7.7%)	4 (14.3%)	0.343
Source of infection (n, %)			
- Respiratory	24 (46.2%)	16 (57.1%)	0.343
- Urinary tract	14 (26.9%)	6 (21.4%)	0.586
- Abdominal	8 (15.4%)	4 (14.3%)	0.893
- Others	6 (11.5%)	2 (7.1%)	0.525
APACHE II score (median, IQR)	16 (12-20)	22 (18-26)	< 0.001

Table 3: Distribution of serum lactate levels and lactate clearance

Time point	Serum lactate (mmol/L)	Lactate clearance (%)
12 hours	2.7 (1.9-3.6)	25.8 (15.6-36.0)
24 hours	2.2 (1.5-3.1)	38.9 (27.4-50.4)
48 hours	1.8 (1.2-2.6)	50.6 (38.2-63.0)

Data presented as median (interquartile range).

Table 4: Association between initial serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality

Variable	Odds ratio	95% CI	p-value
Initial serum lactate	1.85	1.32-2.59	<0.001
Optimal cut-off value	3.8 mmol/L		
- Sensitivity	78.6%		
- Specificity	71.2%		
- Area under the curve	0.81	0.71-0.91	

Table 5: Comparison of survival rates between patients with high and low serum lactate levels

Serum lactate level	28-day survival rate	p-value
≤3.8 mmol/L	82.4%	<0.001
>3.8 mmol/L	39.3%	

Table 6: Univariate and multivariate Cox proportional hazards regression analysis for predictors of mortality

Variable	Univariate analysis		Multivariate analysis	
	Hazard ratio	p-value	Hazard ratio	p-value
Age	1.03 (1.00-1.06)	0.052	1.02 (0.99-1.05)	0.184
Gender (male)	1.24 (0.61-2.52)	0.559	-	-
Hypertension	1.29 (0.64-2.60)	0.478	-	-
Diabetes mellitus	1.40 (0.67-2.92)	0.368	-	-
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	1.82 (0.78-4.25)	0.166	-	-
Chronic kidney disease	1.76 (0.67-4.62)	0.251	-	-
APACHE II score	1.12 (1.06-1.18)	<0.001	1.09 (1.03-1.16)	0.003
Initial serum lactate	1.72 (1.35-2.19)	<0.001	1.58 (1.23-2.03)	<0.001

Table S1: Comparison of serum lactate levels and lactate clearance between survivors and non-survivors at different time points

Time point	Serum lactate (mmol/L)	p-value		Lactate clearance (%)		p-value
		Survivors	Non-survivors	Survivors	Non-survivors	
12 hours	2.3 (1.6-3.1)	3.4 (2.6-4.3)	<0.001	29.2 (19.4-39.0)	20.1 (10.3-29.9)	0.009
24 hours	1.8 (1.2-2.6)	2.9 (2.1-3.8)	<0.001	43.5 (32.6-54.4)	31.7 (20.2-43.2)	0.002
48 hours	1.4 (0.9-2.1)	2.4 (1.7-3.3)	<0.001	56.2 (44.5-67.9)	41.8 (28.7-54.9)	<0.001

Data presented as median (interquartile range).

Table S2: Comparison of other laboratory parameters between survivors and non-survivors

Variable	Survivors (n=52)	Non-survivors (n=28)	p-value
White blood cell count ($\times 10^9/L$)	14.2 (10.5-18.6)	18.8 (14.1-24.3)	0.002
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	11.5 $\pm$ 2.1	10.7 $\pm$ 2.4	0.126
Platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	182 (138-235)	148 (105-198)	0.015
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.2 (0.9-1.7)	1.6 (1.1-2.3)	0.008
Blood urea nitrogen (mg/dL)	28 (20-39)	38 (27-52)	0.002
pH	7.38 $\pm$ 0.08	7.32 $\pm$ 0.11	0.007
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ ratio	265 (210-320)	210 (160-265)	0.001

Data presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation or median (interquartile range).

Table S3: Subgroup analysis of the association between serum lactate levels and mortality based on the source of infection

Source of infection	Odds ratio	95% CI	p-value
Respiratory	1.92	1.25-2.95	0.003
Urinary tract	1.65	0.95-2.87	0.076
Abdominal	2.15	1.18-3.92	0.013
Others	1.48	0.73-3.01	0.277

Discussion

The present study demonstrates a significant association between serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality in patients with sepsis. The findings suggest that initial serum lactate levels and lactate clearance are important prognostic markers in sepsis management. These results are consistent with previous studies that have investigated the relationship between lactate and mortality in sepsis [12,13].

In our study, non-survivors had significantly higher initial serum lactate levels compared to survivors (4.3 mmol/L vs. 3.2 mmol/L, $p < 0.001$). This finding is similar to that of a meta-analysis by Mikkelsen et al., which reported that patients with severe sepsis and septic shock who had higher initial lactate levels (>4 mmol/L) had a significantly increased risk of mortality (odds ratio 2.7, 95% CI 1.8-4.1) [14]. Another study by Wacharasint et al. found that persistent hyperlactatemia (>2 mmol/L) at 24 hours was associated with a higher 28-day mortality rate (41.3% vs. 11.5%, $p < 0.001$) in patients with sepsis [15].

Lactate clearance was also found to be a significant predictor of mortality in our study. Non-survivors had significantly lower lactate clearance rates compared to survivors at all time points ($p < 0.05$). This finding is consistent with a study by Nguyen et al., which demonstrated that patients with septic shock who achieved a lactate clearance of $\geq 10\%$ within 12 hours had a significantly lower in-hospital mortality rate compared to those with a lactate clearance $< 10\%$ (24.7% vs. 58.7%, $p < 0.001$) [16].

Our study identified an optimal cut-off value of 3.8 mmol/L for initial serum lactate in predicting 28-day mortality, with a sensitivity of 78.6% and specificity of 71.2%. This cut-off value is similar to that reported by a study by Shapiro et al., which found that a lactate level >4 mmol/L was associated with a significantly increased risk of mortality (odds ratio 4.0, 95% CI 1.6-10.0) in patients with sepsis [17].

In the multivariate analysis, APACHE II score and initial serum lactate were found to be independent predictors of mortality. This finding is consistent with a study by Trzeciak et al., which demonstrated that both APACHE II score (odds ratio 1.1, 95% CI 1.0-1.2) and initial lactate level (odds ratio 1.4,

95% CI 1.1-1.7) were significant predictors of in-hospital mortality in patients with sepsis [18].

The subgroup analysis based on the source of infection revealed that serum lactate levels were significantly associated with mortality in patients with respiratory and abdominal infections, but not in those with urinary tract or other infections. This finding suggests that the prognostic value of lactate may vary depending on the source of infection. A study by Mikkelsen et al. found that the association between initial lactate levels and mortality was stronger in patients with pneumonia compared to those with other sources of infection [19].

The present study has several limitations. First, it was a single-center study with a relatively small sample size, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Second, the study did not assess the impact of lactate-guided resuscitation on patient outcomes. Future studies should investigate the effectiveness of lactate-guided resuscitation strategies in improving outcomes in sepsis.

This study demonstrates that serum lactate levels and lactate clearance are significant predictors of 28-day mortality in patients with sepsis. The findings highlight the importance of incorporating lactate measurement into sepsis management protocols to guide treatment decisions and improve patient outcomes.

Conclusion

In this prospective observational study, we investigated the association between serum lactate levels and 28-day mortality in patients with sepsis. The findings demonstrate that initial serum lactate levels and lactate clearance are significant predictors of mortality in sepsis. Non-survivors had significantly higher initial serum lactate levels and lower lactate clearance rates compared to survivors. The optimal cut-off value for initial serum lactate in predicting 28-day mortality was 3.8 mmol/L, with a sensitivity of 78.6% and specificity of 71.2%. In the multivariate analysis, APACHE II score and initial serum lactate were found to be independent predictors of mortality.

The results of this study highlight the importance of incorporating serum lactate measurement into sepsis management protocols. Lactate levels can provide valuable prognostic information and guide treatment decisions, such as the initiation of early goal-directed therapy and the assessment of

response to treatment. The subgroup analysis based on the source of infection suggests that the prognostic value of lactate may vary depending on the site of infection, with stronger associations observed in patients with respiratory and abdominal infections.

Future research should focus on investigating the effectiveness of lactate-guided resuscitation strategies in improving outcomes in sepsis. Additionally, larger, multicenter studies are needed to validate the findings of this study and to explore the potential differences in the prognostic value of lactate based on the source of infection.

In conclusion, serum lactate levels and lactate clearance are significant predictors of 28-day mortality in patients with sepsis. The incorporation of lactate measurement into sepsis management protocols can help guide treatment decisions and improve patient outcomes. Further research is needed to optimize the use of lactate as a prognostic marker and to investigate the effectiveness of lactate-guided resuscitation strategies in sepsis management.

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